

ACHITECTURE

SUBJECTIVE EVALUATION OF THE ACOUSTIC PERFORMANCE OF THREE MUSIC CLASSROOMS IN A BULGARIAN SCHOOL: COMPLIANCE WITH STANDARDS AND AGE-BASED PREFERENCES

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Abstract

The acoustic environment plays a crucial role in the effectiveness of music education. This study presents a comparative subjective evaluation of three different classrooms used for music instruction in a Bulgarian school. A standardized music piece was performed and recorded in each room, and the recordings were subsequently played back to two age groups of students. A structured survey was administered to assess their personal perceptions of parameters such as clarity, reverberation, and overall acoustic comfort. The findings reveal notable differences in acoustic preference between younger and older students, with older students' responses more closely aligning with established acoustic standards for music spaces. Importantly, objective analysis indicates that only one of the three classrooms complies with the recommended acoustic criteria for musical function. These results underscore the need for targeted acoustic improvements, particularly in classrooms used by younger students, to ensure optimal learning conditions tailored to their perceptual and developmental needs.

Keywords: Sound quality, school acoustic, building acoustics, Acoustic layout of music classrooms

I. INTRODUCTION

The acoustic treatment of music rooms is essential for both perception and health of the students. From the author's observations, as well as from impressions in various publications, it has been established that there is a lack of comprehensive rating and a treatment of the music training facilities in accordance with the students' needs.

The national standard gives very generalized requirements, sometimes with only one reverberation time value, which was considered insufficient to establish a quality music experience.

The present study poses more detailed evaluation questions regarding personal perception as well as the specific impact of the rooms on the students and their learning ability depending on the different acoustic

treatment of the rooms, emphasizing on the initial impact of sound perception.

II. METHOD

A. Location

The analysis was made in three music classrooms of different sizes and different acoustic treatments.

- A room for individual music lessons
- A standard classroom
- A music studio

The sizes and the special configuration of the premises are shown in Table 1.

The three rooms are part of a standard school, but with very different indicators. Our aim is to examine the way the students perceive the different acoustic processing and how the dimensions and the sound affect them.

Table 1

Evaluated music rooms dimensions and appearances

	L [m]	W [m]	H [m]	Picture
Room 1 individual music lessons	6	4	3,35	
Room 2 Classroom	8,5	6	3,35	
Room 3 Music Studio	5,8	3,8	3,35	

According to the standard guidelines for music rooms, the requirement for reverberation time for rooms with that volume is 0.6 seconds. [1].

In some Standards as the American National Standard

Acoustical Performance [2] is given the Minimum surface area of acoustical treatment for different sound absorption coefficients, ceiling heights, and reverberation times.

Some national Standards contain Recommended Reverberation Times for Small Music Rooms for different Music Activity Space [3].

The requirement according to DIN 18041 [4] of Reverberation time for music rehearsal room with this volume would be: Room 1 – 0,56 s, Room 2 – 0,69 s and Room 3 – 0,55 s.

Usually, studies evaluate the acoustical performance, regarding its Reverberation Time, Background Noise Level and Airborne Sound Insulation between rooms [5]. In the current premises, only the third one is close to these requirements (*cf. Fig 1*). This was due to its shape and characteristics but also enhanced by multiple performance acoustic panels and elements that were installed.

Fig.1. Range of reverberation time as a function of frequency according to DIN 18041 – Room 3

B. Participants

We chose to run the survey among 2 different age groups: 42 older students (about 18 years old) and 27 younger ones (about 13 years old). Younger participants are pupils at the music school used for

this survey when the older ones are first year students from the University of Architecture, Civil Engineering and Geodesy, Physics Department.

C. Procedure

Figure 2: The sound of the violin in rooms 1, 2 and 3

The same musical piece is played on a violin in each room from a professional musician and then recorded. The sound of the violin in the three rooms can be demonstrated in Fig.2.

The figure shows the sound profile, with greater deviations observed in the first two rooms.

The recording was played separately in front of the two groups of students and they were given a questionnaire for each recording.

The prepared questionnaire consisted of 3 questions on the acoustics of the rooms, overall preferences of the room and an opened question on the effect the recording had on them. The numerical responses were in the form of a 6-point scale, in which 1 indicated low rating of the acoustics and perception and 6 indicated a high rating.

An analysis of the three rooms on the point system was made, as well as a spontaneous description of the impact.

III. RESULTS

The results of the survey analysis are shown in Fig 3 and Fig 4. An analysis of the questionnaire was according to the point system. In addition, information

Fig 3: Comparative study of the sound conditions of the room with ratings from students from upper grades.

Fig 4: Comparative study of the sound conditions of the room with ratings from students from lower grades.

These results show not only the different perception of the students and the requirement for appropriate processing of the premises, but also the need to find a more flexible approach that connects human sensations with the standard requirements for the premises. Further study can be led in order to find the optimal studying conditions taking in consideration changes in age characteristics and needs.

Sound is much more than a vibration. It is an emotion, it is well-being, a sensation, it gives information about feelings, preferences, attitudes, about the state of person. It is something alive and changing with a person and a person's life and development. Acoustics can contribute not only to a more effective music education but also – to a better perception of the world.

was collected on the spontaneous description of the impact.

Differences depending on both age and gender are observed. For the purpose of this study we decided to analyse only the differences in age and later – expose and analyse the differences in age and sex with the help of a specialist.

The personal sensations of the students generally show a higher preference for the third room, which has enhanced sound absorption. But younger students show more varied preferences.

Students described used the following to describe the sound and acoustics in the first classroom: excitement, tension, highest density of sound, piercing, intrusive sound, more effort, sharp, superimposed, truncated, squeaky, clean and well-directed sound when listening, uncleaned, resounding, muffled.

Perceptions about the third room were: voluminous, clear, clean and soft sound, muted, mystery, calm, pleasant feeling, harmonious, the sound is purest, balance at different frequencies, balanced but strong, pleasant dense, good acoustics, purest tone, emotionally pleasant, relaxing, mystery, tranquillity.

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